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ENHANCING HIGH-FLOW HYDROGEN REFUELING: MITIGATION OF PRESSURE LOSSES IN STORAGE AND DELIVERY SYSTEMS

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- Motivation
- Problem definition
- Methodology and solution procedure
- Results
- Conclusion and discussion

- High-flow hydrogen refueling is essential for heavy-duty vehicles (trucks, buses).
- Main challenge: significant pressure losses in storage and delivery systems.
- Compliance with SAE J2601/5 fueling protocols.
- Issue addressed within the framework of the National Hydrogen Mobility Center.

Historical average NEDC and WLTP CO₂ emission values and targets for new passenger cars without flexible compliance mechanisms ¹

T National Hydrogen Mobility Center

T Centre established in the framework of the implementation of the Hydrogen Strategy for a Climate Neutral Europe and the Hydrogen Strategy of the Czech Republic, which reflects the goal of the Green Deal for Europe - to achieve climate neutrality by 2050.

T TN02000007-008 Hydrogen filling ecosystem at rates exceeding 60 g H₂/s

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T Objective:

T To create a model of a bundle of 12 pressure cylinders as a buffer for a fast filling station for road vehicles exceeding a speed of 60g H₂/s.

T Requirements:

- T** Station consisting of 12 pressure cylinders with a maximum pressure of up to 330 bar (operating pressure 300 bar)
- T** Cylinder type MAWP 330 bar
- T** Operating temperature -20 to 40 °C
- T** Analysis of flow rates, cylinder temperatures, and pressure inside the cylinders
- T** Analysis of problematic nodes during rapid filling

T Problem definition:

T The main obstacle to fast refueling of heavy vehicles such as trucks and buses is managing pressure losses throughout the system.

T Critical Points and Losses:

- T** Pressure losses are most pronounced in narrow and geometrically complex sections of piping.

T Impact on efficiency:

- T** High flow rates exacerbate pressure losses in pipes and components.
- T** This affects the station's ability to maintain the required pressure ramp rates specified by standards such as SAE J2601/5.
- T** Pressure losses reduce efficiency and may require higher power input from compressors and cooling systems.

T Technological barriers:

- T** Lack of commercially available and standardized components (such as hoses, valves, and nozzles) capable of handling flow rates above 65 g/s at 70 MPa.

HYDROGEN REFUELING STATION SIMULATION MODEL

- Model based on an existing refueling station in Vítkovice, Czech Republic
- 1D simulations in GT-Suite with GEM-3D plug-in
- FluidRefrigerant template** (GT-Suite) – advanced thermo-fluid modeling of gases and liquids
- Hydrogen properties from **REFPROP** (NIST)
- Maxwell equation** of state – accurate prediction of H₂ behavior at high pressures and phase transitions
- Captures **Joule–Thomson effect** during expansion processes
- Recommended for hydrogen modeling:
 - High-pressure gas (350 / 700 bar)
 - Two-phase flow (e.g., cryogenic fueling systems)
- Simulated range: 100–300 g/s, 150–300 bar

INITIAL CYLINDER BUNDLE DESIGN

- T** The first design model of the bundle consisted of tubes with a diameter of 6 mm, which were then connected to a wider tube with a diameter of 12 mm. This tube ran through the centre of the bundle and was shaped so that the outlet fitting of the bundle was in the desired position (both horizontal and vertical).
- T** The initial configuration of the cylinder bundle resulted in excessively high pressure losses up to **17.4 bar**, and such a bundle would not be suitable for the planned filling station.
- T** The greatest pressure losses were achieved on the central tube (**5.68 bar**) and in the connection of the first pair of cylinders in the bundle (**5.17 bar**).

MODIFIED CYLINDER BUNDLE DESIGN

- Increased pipe diameter up to 14 mm
- Reduced number of bends
- Improved flow distribution → reduced pressure losses
- removal of most elbows
- gradual expansion of piping from cylinders (reduction in the number of large-diameter pipes)
- use of bends instead of elbows when connecting cylinders to the bundle

- Significant reduction in pressure losses.
- < 3 bar loss at 100–200 g/s under all tested conditions
- Worst case (extreme): 7.95 bar total pressure loss (only a model for capturing marginal phenomena)

The most critical points of the bundle - DEVINN

Total pressure loss of the bottle bundle - varianta DEVINN

Effective mitigation of pressure losses is critical for high-flow H₂ refuelling (>100 g/s, buses & trucks).

Original cylinder bundle design:

- excessive pressure losses
- limiting high-flow capability

Redesigned system:

- Pressure losses < **3 bar at 100–200 g/s**
- Fully compliant with SAE J2601/5 protocols
- Reduced number of bends
- removal of most elbows
- gradual expansion of piping from cylinders (reduction in the number of large-diameter pipes)
- use of bends instead of elbows when connecting cylinders to the bundle
- Usage of standardized components

MODEL OF 550 BAR CYLINDER BUNDLE

COMPLEX MODEL OF THE REFUELING STATION

- capacity to fill at mass flow of up to 240 g/s (150 g/s)
- Fill empty tanks (50 bar) to 300 bar in 105 s (150 s)
- Necessary to create a **control algorithm** for setting the bundle switching (currently the only condition to keep the mass flux above 150 g/s) – **vehicle limitation**
- Vehicle tank temperature issues**
- Need for more detailed modeling of the **cooling system** (cooperation with Czech Technical University in Prague) - cooling capacity up to **153 kW** for cooling to **-40 °C**

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Thank you for your attention!

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